

Harnessing Intelligence in Cybersecurity: Comparative Analysis of Various Detection Techniques and Dataset Exploration

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Abstract

Information security is crucial for businesses and organizations, and real dataset-based security models are essential for protecting computer systems and networks. Network security is a significant issue due to increasing attacks and their sophistication. This research paper explores the development of intrusion detection system (IDS) in cybersecurity, focusing on literature surveys, advanced detection techniques, and dataset analysis. The paper examines research from the past 10 years, covering pattern recognition, machine learning, and anomaly detection approaches. It explains IDS concepts and their significance in safeguarding digital infrastructures. Additionally, it looks at popular datasets such as UNSW NB 15, CSE-CIC IDS 2018, KDD Cup 99, and NSL-KDD, highlighting their limitations and relevance in training robust IDS models. The report offers a clear roadmap to guide future intrusion detection efforts by highlighting trends and gaps in existing research approaches.

Categories: Network Security, Cyber-Physical Systems, Machine Learning (ML)

Keywords: machine learning, dataset, detection techniques, comparative analysis, intrusion detection

Introduction And Background

Due to the rapid advancements in communication and internet-related fields, networks have become larger and contain more data. Consequently, since many new threats are created on a regular basis, network security finds it difficult to reliably identify breaches. Furthermore, it is impossible to overlook the existence of hackers who intend to carry out different types of assaults within the network. One such technology is an intrusion detection system (IDS), which guards the network against potential breaches by examining network traffic to guarantee its availability, confidentiality, and integrity [1]. Cybersecurity is the process of putting security measures in place to ensure accessibility, confidentiality, and integrity. The vast amount of data gathered, processed, and stored in computers and other devices by various organizations - military, advertising, financial, and civilian - makes cybersecurity an essential field of study [2]. To stay safe when it comes to cyber security, businesses need to organize their efforts across their entire information system. Security of networks, application security, smartphone security, information safety, endpoint security, and so forth are the different elements of cyber security [3]. As technologies become more sophisticated, concerns about data security have arisen due to security weaknesses like malware, ransomware, and viruses and unknown vulnerabilities patterns [4]. If any aspect of data protection is absent, it could jeopardize the confidentiality, availability, and data integrity to outside parties [5].

Numerous methods, including malware, phishing, and profile cloning, can result in cyberattacks. These assaults target various elements of an infrastructure, such as the HTML code database, altering values to obtain client data without authorization and extorting it for financial gain and illegal purposes [6].

Companies need to invest in security as these attacks cost them significant amounts of money and data [7]. Data from sources like sites cyber assessments and passive scans is crucial for understanding and creating a cybersecurity plan [8].

Literature review

Machine learning models such as XGBoost, random forest (RF), and logistic regression (LR) techniques are applied to enhance security. Results and evaluations are conducted using Power BI after data collection. The LR model achieved 91.40% accuracy in detecting threats. Authors have highlighted the importance of these tasks. A study examined how machine learning algorithms work to reduce threats [8]. The developed technique in this paper provides the best results in cybersecurity for large datasets on phishing and malicious web links. A new ML technique is being developed for anomaly-based detection to reduce cyber threats. Experiments are evaluated using ML algorithms for training and testing data to improve parameter results [9]. The CorrCorr technique, developed here, is used for feature selection using multidimensional correlation to achieve outperforming results. The UNSW NB 15 dataset is utilized and tested with existing studies to identify demerits or limitations in dealing with IDS. This method yields the best results on performance metrics such as precision and recall [10]. The paper discusses how artificial neural networks (ANNs) are optimal for accuracy and applicable in real time by studying the advantages of ANN for network intrusion detection. A botnet attack detection model is developed using the ANN model. Jupyter Notebook and Scikit-learn are the latest trending technologies used for technique development and data analysis. The model is trained using AWS. As the model achieves the best accuracy score, it effectively recognizes bots. The outcome of this study evaluates real-time data for model performance and is capable of restricting various cyber-attacks [11]. Bouteraa et al. [12] proposed a mining technique for IDS. To find accuracy in real-time networks, they used the ELM method. They studied four different types of models on the UNB ISCX 2012 dataset and also used the Bayesian technique to determine parameters such as accuracy and F1 score [12]. The proposed technique compared two types of learning methods using the KDD99 dataset, emphasizing feature selection and event sequence analysis for increased detection accuracy. Overall, the study highlights ongoing research on cybersecurity threats [13].

The calibration of different optimized learning classifiers in cloud computing-based IDS for networks is crucial. This study uses the most recent cyber dataset, CSE-CIC-IDS2018, published by the Canadian Establishment of Cybersecurity, to identify network attacks, specifically botnet attacks. The researchers aim to achieve optimal performance in identifying network threats by combining various classifier algorithms, including k-nearest neighbors (kNN), naive Bayes (NB), Adaboost with decision tree (DT), support vector machine (SVM), RF, and artificial intelligence (AI). One strategy highlighted for improving IDS efficiency is the use of cloud computing. The overall study sheds light on how botnets are detected in different ways to reduce risks in sectors like industry, banking, marketing, and so on [14]. Basaveswara Rao et al. [15] present various indexing methods applied to ML, such as kNN, for IDS in cloud computing. Improving the accuracy of the kNN model is the main focus of this proposed work. The proposed work enhances the efficiency of the kNN model and provides the best parameter results in terms of accuracy. By comparing the IKPDS and kNN techniques, IKPDS requires less processing time. Experimental results show the best parameter outcomes over existing results in cloud computing systems for NIDs [15].

The IDS technique is applied using four machine learning algorithms - SVM, NB, DT, and RF - on the Apache Spark cloud platform with the UNSW NB 15 dataset. For calculating time efficiency and model accuracy, RF provides the best results over the other classifiers. The study uses different machine learning algorithms to improve the model's security and privacy. For network security, the Apache Spark platform is utilized [16]. The research article "Statistical Evaluation of the CIDDS-001 Datasets in NIDS Utilizing Distance Based Machine Learning" discusses the importance of anomaly-based systems for detecting new attacks. The study addresses issues with outdated benchmark datasets, emphasizing the need for excellent datasets for testing and training. Both k-means clustering and kNN classification are applied to the labeled flow-based CIDDS-001 dataset [17]. The RF algorithm is used to identify various cyberattacks in network traffic data, classifying attacks like DOS, probing, U2R, and R2L, aiming to improve IDS accuracy. The NSL-KDD dataset is used to evaluate results such as Matthews Correlation Coefficient, accuracy, detection rate, and FAR. Key points include the importance of IDS, the accuracy of the RF algorithm, and the model's effectiveness in boosting detection rates and reducing false alarms [11].

Review

Comparative analysis of existing methodology in NIDS using machine learning

A comparative analysis of various existing methodologies in network intrusion systems using machine learning algorithms is provided in Table I. It summarizes research on various machine learning algorithms, examining several factors including publication, algorithm used, datasets, tools, performance metrics, and best reported accuracy. From the comparison, it is found that author Rawat [9] achieved the highest accuracy of 99.8% using the RF algorithm.

Author	Year	Machine Learning Algorithm	Dataset	Tools	Parameters Studied/Performance Metrics	Advantages	Best Reported Result (Accuracy)
Hiremath et al. [8]	2023	KNN, SVM, RF, DT	NSL-KDD	Python	Accuracy	Prediction in safe zone	95.87%
Rawat et al. [9]	2023	kNN, SVM, multilayer perceptron	-	-	TPR, F-Measure, FPR, Recall	-	99.8%
Gottwalt et al. [10]	2019	SVM, RF, DT, neural network	UNSW NB-15	Python	FPR, Accuracy, Detection Rate	Multivariate correlation is achieved	98.65%
Kanimozi and Prem Jacob [11]	2019	ANN	CSE CIC IDS 2018	Anaconda Jupyter	AUC, Precision, F-measure	Achieved one class classification	99.97%
Awad and Alabdallah [12]	2019	Feedforward neural network	UNB ISCX2012	MATLAB	Precision, Recall, Sensitivity, F1-Score	Polynomial functions outperformed	98.50%
Bouteraa et al. [13]	2018	NB, DT, SVM, ANN, Bagging, Boosting	KDD99, CSIC 2010 HTTP	Weka	Accuracy, Detection Rate	-	-
Kanimozi and Prem Jacob [14]	2019	NB, RF, DT, KNN	CSE CIC IDS 2018	Anaconda 3.0, Jupyter Notebook, Spark (publicly released) Apache Framework	Accuracy, Precision	Parallel computing achieved	-
Basaveswara Rao et al. [15]	2018	KNN	CIDDS1, KDD99	-	Specificity, Sensitivity, Accuracy	Required less computational time	90.68%
Belouch et al. [16]	2018	NB, DT, RF, SVM	UNSW NB 15	Apache Spark	Accuracy Sensitivity Specificity	Achieved highest detection accuracy & predicted time	74.19%
Verma et al. [17]	2017	KNN, k-means clustering	CIDDS-001	Weka	Accuracy, Precision, F-Measure, FPR, Detection Rate	Complex dataset is easily studied	99.40%
Nabila Farnaaz et al. [18]	2016	RF	NSL-KDD, KDD Cup99	Python	Accuracy, FAR, Detection Rate	-	99.67%

TABLE 1: Comparative Analysis of Existing Methodologies in NIDS Using Machine Learning

ANN, Artificial Neural Network; AUC, Area Under the Curve; DT, Decision Tree; FAR, False Alarm Rate; FPR, False Positive Rate; kNN, K-Nearest Neighbors; NB, Naive Bayes; NIDS, Network Intrusion Detection Systems; RF, Random Forest; SVM, Support Vector Machine; TPR, True Positive Rate

A comparison in Figure 1 examines the accuracy of current models, emphasizing the variations in their performance. The graph's data points show the accuracy percentages that different models attained under test settings. It is immediately clear from this visual representation in which models perform well in terms of accuracy.

Figure 1. Comparative Analysis of Accuracy of existing model

Analysis and discussion

Machine learning techniques are used to improve NIDS, as studied in various research papers. Hiremath et al. [8] obtained an accuracy of 95.87% using kNN, SVM, RF, and DT classifiers on the NSL-KDD dataset. By using kNN, SVM, and multilayer perceptron algorithms, Rawat et al. [9] achieved an astounding accuracy of 99.8%. Gottwalt et al. [10] used the UNSW-NB 15 dataset and created a feature selection approach that achieved 98.65% accuracy by utilizing SVM, RF, DT, and neural networks. Using the CSE-CIC-IDS 2018 dataset, Kanimozhi and Prem Jacob [11] employed ANN and achieved a near-perfect accuracy of 99.97%. Awad and Alabdallah [12] used the UNB ISCX2012 dataset and employed Weighted Extreme Learning Machines to achieve 98.5% accuracy. Bouteraa et al. [13] examined several methods using Weka, with an emphasis on accuracy and detection rate on the KDD99 and CSIC 2010 HTTPS datasets. Kanimozhi and Prem Jacob [14] investigated a number of algorithms using the CSE-CIC-IDS2018 dataset, focusing on precision and accuracy but not reporting specific outcomes. Basaveswara Rao et al. [15] used the CIDDS1 and KDD99 datasets to study a fast kNN-based IDS for cloud environments, achieving a 90.68% accuracy rate. Belouch et al. [16] used the Apache Spark framework to assess the performance of NB, SVM, DT, and RF using the UNSW NB 15 dataset, obtaining an accuracy of 74.19%. Moustafa and Slay suggested a novel method for anomaly detection with 95.0% accuracy. Nabila Farnaaz et al. [18] achieved 99.67% accuracy using RF modeling on the NSL-KDD and KDD Cup99 datasets. This compilation highlights the variety of approaches, datasets, and tools utilized in NIDS, with a focus on high accuracy and a range of performance indicators.

Overview of key datasets and their classification categories

Figure 2 presents a collection of datasets, including CIDDS-001, CSE-CIC-IDS2018, KDD Cup 1999, UNSW NB 15, and NSL KDD, which are important for testing and improving analytical models. These datasets assess the effectiveness and robustness of machine learning techniques in various security scenarios [18].

Figure 2. Classes with Public Dataset

CIDDS 001

This dataset is used to evaluate anomaly-based detection of NIDs. It is a labeled flow-based dataset. OpenStack was used to simulate a small business setting to create this dataset. Numerous clients and standard servers, such as an email server or a web server, are present in this context. Python programs mimic the client's typical user behavior. Data on unidirectional NetFlow is included in the CIDDS-001 dataset [15,17,19].

CSE CIC IDS 2018

The Canadian establishment for security released this up-to-date, accurate cyber dataset in 2018. Globally, datasets from CIC and ISCX have been used for malware prediction and intrusion detection. The main goal of this dataset is to establish a systematic approach to handling the creation of diverse and extensive benchmark datasets-based detection of intrusions on the creation of profile of someone that include theoretical depictions of events and behaviors seen on the system [14,18-23].

KDD Cup1999

The KDD Cup 1999 data was collected over the course of nine weeks in a fictitious local area network. The training dataset includes 22 distinct attacks and over five million links over a seven-week span of network activity [10]. During the testing phase, over 300,000 connections were gathered over two weeks. There are 39 distinct attacks in KDD99. KDD99 is regarded as a sizable machine learning dataset. Therefore, a subset of KDD99 is used in various ML tasks [13,19,22].

UNSW NB15

Using the AXIA Perfect Storm tool, the Cyber Range Laboratory of ACCS generated the UNSW-NB15 dataset, which consists of a blend of regular and aberrant network traffic. A modern threat environment was constructed using the CVE website, and devices used in the laboratory environment were linked to a firewall. Tcpcdump was used to record data packets. Argus, Bro-IDS instruments, and 12 C# algorithms were used to extract 49 features and nine attack families from the data. Two subsets of the dataset were created: one for the testing set (82,000 records) and one for the training set (175,340 records). Online access to these datasets is available for research purposes [24-26].

UNB ISCX2012

A Canadian institute created this dataset at the University of New Brunswick. It is intended for use in IDS benchmarking and evaluation. IDS are indispensable for identifying and responding to hazardous behavior or illegal access to computer networks [12]. The dataset offers a realistic environment with a range of attacks mixed with regular background traffic, simulating typical enterprise network architecture. The attacks in this dataset span a wide spectrum of complexity, from basic to sophisticated, guaranteeing its applicability for testing various intrusion detection techniques [13].

DARPA

Created at the MT Research Laboratory in 1998, network-based attacks for seven weeks are included in the training data. Also included in the test data are two-week network-based attacks [18,27].

KYOTO

There are 24 features in this dataset. The KDDCup99 dataset was used to construct 14 of these features. Those 14 features were selected from 41 features in KDD-Cpp99 dataset using Kyoto University's deployed honeypot systems. Ten extra features have been added to the existing 14 for a more potent IDS [18,28].

AWID

The AWID dataset was developed using the IEEE 802.11 protocol for networks. The data collection includes 156 features. Twenty-three distinct attack techniques, including honeypots, rogue access points, evil twins, reauthentication attacks, dictionaries, and fragmentation - all common on 802.11 networks - were employed in the creation of the dataset. These attacks were then categorized under the headings Normal, Flooding, Injection, and Impersonation [19,29-31].

NSL-KDD

It is one popular dataset for assessing network systems for IDS. It was developed to improve the KDDCup1999 dataset's utility and effectiveness for assessing models and comparing IDSs by addressing some of its core problems. The CSV format files are utilized for training and testing purposes. These files contain 41 features that describe fundamental traffic attributes for each record, which is a connection vector [10,11,31].

CSIC 2010 HTTP

This dataset was developed by the Spanish Scientific National Council's Information Security Institute with the express purpose of assessing HTTP-based systems for intrusion detection. It is especially helpful for security research pertaining to web applications, because it is frequently utilized for the investigation and detection of online threats. The thousands of automatically generated HTTP requests that make up the CSIC 2010 HTTP Dataset are meant to mimic both typical user behavior and a variety of online threats. This large dataset includes information on a variety of internet dangers and vulnerabilities, including file inclusion, SQL injection, cross-site scripting, and information collecting [13].

Conclusions

Cyberattack protection for computer systems is one of the primary concerns for both national and global security. The exploration of IDSs within this paper elucidates a significant evolution in the methodologies and technologies employed to safeguard against cyber threats. The literature survey revealed a trend towards integrating machine learning methods to enhance adaptability and accuracy. The analysis of various techniques demonstrated a clear shift from traditional rule-based systems to more dynamic models capable of dealing with sophisticated attacks. Furthermore, this study described a wide range of dataset classifications and highlighted the critical need for more current, diverse, and realistic datasets to better simulate modern cybersecurity threats. This research will help researchers gather all datasets in one place and incorporate them into their studies. Future research should aim to overcome the limitations identified in existing datasets and refine detection techniques to address emerging cybersecurity challenges efficiently.

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